

LINEAR RESPONSE OF TWO-PHASE COMPOSITES WITH CROSS MODULI: EXACT UNIVERSAL RELATIONS

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ABSTRACT

We consider the linear-response properties of composites made of two isotropic materials. We concentrate on linear-response phenomena, with nonvanishing cross coefficients, such as the magnetoelectric effect, the thermoelectric effect, and coupled, multispecies diffusion. We find that the moduli of the composite must obey a number of compatibility relations, involving the moduli of the components, but totally independent of the mixture ratio of the components and the microstructure of the composite. The compatibility conditions take the form: $C(L, L_a, L_b) \equiv LL_b^{-1}L_b - L_bL_a^{-1}L = 0$, where L_aL_b are the response matrices of the components, and L is that of the composite. These come about because there exists a choice of driving force and fluxes—an eigenbasis—that are decoupled in both components. When the composite itself is isotropic, these constitute $n(n-1)/2$ relations that its moduli must obey (for real response matrices), leaving only n independent coefficients to be specified— n being the number of driving fields. When the composite is anisotropic, the elements of L are spatial tensors and the same conditions apply as relations between these tensors. In the latter case one can eliminate the moduli of the components, and obtain relations that the moduli of the composite must satisfy among themselves. The mere fact that the composite is made of two isotropic components, without any further information, imposes strong relations among its moduli. For example, we show that all the tensor moduli of such a composite must be symmetric. The same compatibility conditions must also be obeyed by the response matrices of any three composites of the same two isotropic components; so, knowledge of the moduli of two composites supplies constraints on any third, or, for that matter, on the components themselves. We discuss the general properties of the compatibility conditions and their possible relation to parallel and series construction of composites, and demonstrate our findings for the most common case of two driving fields in three dimensions. The compatibility conditions apply not only for the effective response matrices of well homogenized composites, but also for the local response at any point within some region that is filled with an arbitrary two-phase mixture—to the potentials on the boundary of the region. All the above apply, with little change, to the case where the response matrices are complex-symmetric or Hermitian. We have nothing to add to the lore on composites,

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in the case where all the cross coefficients vanish; the compatibility conditions are identities in this case.

I. INTRODUCTION

There exists an enormous lore on the effective linear moduli of composites that are made of two components or phases.^{1,2} Such composites are assumed to be made of intermingled macroscopic regions, each of which is homogeneous and containing one of the two components. The local properties within each of the phases is assumed to be unaffected by the presence of the other or by the granular structure, and to retain the properties it has as a pure substance.

Most of the present knowledge pertains to systems with uncoupled linear-response properties. Particularly noteworthy are the results on bounds of various sorts on the allowed values of the effective constants of two-phase mixtures. Early work³ gave optimal bounds on moduli of isotropic composites such as the dielectric constant, magnetic permeability, electric conductivity and the like. The bounds are function of the moduli of the components and their fractional volumes in the composite and apply to the whole range of possible microstructures that give isotropic composites. These seminal results have since been extended significantly in various directions that we cannot even enumerate here. We note, in particular, the work of Bergman^{4,5} who showed that knowledge of one effective constant, ϵ , of an isotropic composite, contains some information on the microstructure to bound another constant, μ , tighter than is possible without this knowledge. This results in a limited range of allowed pairs of effective constants in the ϵ, μ plane, rather tighter than the allowed rectangle obtained earlier. We also note the extensive generalizations to anisotropic components and composites^{6,7} and to complex moduli^{8,9}.

We shall concern ourselves, in this paper, with the moduli of coupled or cross linear response, in which the application of one driving force induces not only its own associated flux but also other fluxes. The magnetoelectric effect¹⁰ is one example, whereby the application of a magnetic field induces an electric polarization as well as a magnetization, and vice versa. The thermoelectric effect¹¹ is another example in which thermal and electric transports are coupled. Similarly, one finds that, often, the diffusion of particles of different species through some materials or membranes is coupled, involving, so called, cross effects¹².

We will show that in such materials, with nonvanishing cross moduli, the allowed values of the effective moduli of any composite are strongly constrained not only by the known bound, but, in fact, by exact compatibility relations that they must satisfy. Moreover, these relations are oblivious to the volume fractions of the components and the microstructure of the composite. Given only the moduli of the components, those of the composite must obey a large number of universal linear relations among themselves. We assume isotropic components and then, the measurable $n(n+1)/2$ moduli of an isotropic composite (n is the number of driving forces involved) must satisfy $n(n-1)/2$ compatibility conditions, leaving only n independent moduli for such composites. For anisotropic composites, the number of compatibility conditions can be much larger and, in fact the moduli of the components can be eliminated from them altogether, to give relations among the moduli of the composite only. Straley¹³ showed that the three thermoelectric moduli of an isotropic composite of two isotropic components is determined by specifying only two parameters—implying one implicit relation between the three—but he had not arrived at the explicit relation the

moduli-the compatibility conditions. Our results greatly extend his: to the arbitrary n case; to complex response matrices; to anisotropic composites; or for that matter; to general-not necessarily homogenized-systems. Furthermore, we express the results in terms of the explicit, straightforward-to-use compatibility conditions. Such conditions result from the fact that it is possible to choose a basis of driving forces and fluxes, for a two phase system, in which the problem is decoupled in both phases. This fact also underlies Straley's finding.

We give a succinct account of the underlying physics in §II; derive the compatibility conditions in §III; and expound their properties in §V, we generalize to the case of anisotropic composites. Section VI concerns composite, electric circuits as examples of discrete systems that must comply with the compatibility conditions. In §VII, we demonstrate our results for the case of two coupled driving forces. Section VIII summarizes our findings and discusses further issues.

II. CLASSICAL LINEAR-RESPONSE PHENOMENA WITH MIXED COEFFICIENTS

The linear response processes that we deal with are classical phenomena that involve the response of a material to applied driving fields. These processes fall into two categories: What may be called equilibrium response, whereby the system responds to an applied field such as an electric, magnetic, or a gravitational field-by taking up a new equilibrium state (with nonvanishing polarization, magnetization etc.). The other type may be termed flow or dissipation-phenomena. In the latter, a (small) deviation of the system from equilibrium is created by gradients of some potentials such as temperature, electric potential, chemical potential, etc.; this is reacted to by induced currents of appropriate quantities (heat, electric charge, particles, in the above example) that carry the system towards equilibrium.

We shall give a unified treatment for both types of phenomena. Consider a linear-response problem, in a space of arbitrary dimension, d , involving n driving fields, derivable from potentials $\phi = (\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_n)$, and the vector of fluxes $\vec{F} = (\vec{F}_1, \vec{F}_2, \dots, \vec{F}_n)$. When the material is isotropic the fluxes are related to the driving fields in the linear approximation, that we assume all along, by

$$\vec{F} = -L\vec{\nabla}\phi, \quad (1)$$

where L is the $n \times n$ response matrix (which is, in general, position dependent). We assume first that L is real.

The system possesses a generating function:

$$G \equiv \frac{1}{2} \sum L_{km} \vec{\nabla}\phi_k \cdot \vec{\nabla}\phi_m = \frac{1}{2} \sum \vec{F}_i \cdot \vec{\nabla}\phi_i. \quad (2)$$

In the equilibrium case G is some energy function (such as the free energy) that is a functional of the degrees of freedom, ϕ , of the problem. By virtue of the structure of G , L is a symmetric matrix. The functional G attains a minimum in the equilibrium state and for this to be stable, L must be positive definite. Equation (1) expresses the fact that the fluxes are the conjugates of the potentials:

$$F_{k\alpha} = -\frac{\partial G}{\partial(\partial_\alpha\phi_k)}, \quad (3)$$

where α is a space-coordinate index. The Euler-Lagrange equations derived from G are

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{F} = \vec{\nabla} \cdot (L \vec{\nabla} \phi) = 0. \quad (4)$$

Our discussion hinges on linear-response phenomena with nonvanishing cross moduli. A example of an equilibrium cross effect is the magnetoelectric behavior of some materials. Others may be constructed from mechanical systems with approximately quadratic potentials near equilibrium, and gravo-electric effects whereby, a gravitational field can produce ion separation, and induce an electric polarization.

For a dissipation phenomena the role of the generating function is played by the entropy-increase rate¹⁴. The potentials are the partial derivative of the entropy with respect to the densities some extensive quantities (e.g. the thermal potential, T^{-1} is the derivative with respect to the internal energy). The fluxes are the currents of these quantities; also conjugates of the driving potentials in the sense explained in ref 14. One can work, in this case too, with divergenceless fluxes. The elements of L are the kinetic coefficients, and the Onsager reciprocity relations¹⁴ state that the matrix L is symmetric, in general. One exception occurs when one of the intensive parameters on which L depends, in general, is an externally applied magnetic field, H , in which case $L_{km}(H) = L_{mk}(-H)$. We take all along $H = 0$.

Casimir¹⁵ pointed out another exception: When some of the potentials are even under time reversal, say the first k of them, and the rest are odd, then elements of L connecting fields with different time parity are anti symmetric. Then, L takes the form:

$$L = \begin{pmatrix} S^{(1)} & B \\ -\tilde{B} & S^{(2)} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

with $S^{(i)}$ symmetric. We are not aware of a continuous system for which this needs be taken into consideration, and assume thus that the responses matrices we deal with are symmetric; exceptions will then receive a special treatment. As the entropy generation function must be positive, L must be positive in the dissipative case as well.

Example of linear dissipation phenomena are heat diffusion, electric currents, particle diffusion, and cross flows describe the thermoelectric effect, the thermo-magnetic (which is not isotropic) coupled particle diffusion which may also be coupled with thermal diffusion and conduction of electricity¹².

The symmetry and positive definiteness of L , which are compelled by different physical arguments in the two type of phenomena, will play a crucial role in our derivation of the compatibility conditions.

For some systems, the response to driving fields that are time dependent may be described conveniently by the frequency-dependent response matrix. The response can then be described by a complex $L(\omega)$. The driving fields and fluxes are themselves complex with their phases signifying the relative oscillation-phase delays in a particular Fourier component; $L(\omega)$ is still symmetric.

Examples for such a behavior are provided by the magnetoelectric effect in a medium with losses, and electrical circuits which capacitors coils, and ohmic resistors (with we discuss, in more detail in §VI).

We shall be interested in two-phase composites in which L takes the value of the pure component within each grain. The field equation can then be solved, in principle, by solving the Laplace equation, $\Delta\phi_k = 0$, within each region, with the boundary conditions: (i) The potentials ϕ_k are continuous across boundaries, and (ii) The component of the fluxes perpendicular to the boundary is continuous.

III. DERIVATION OF THE COMPATIBILITY RELATIONS

Consider two isotropic substances, a and b , with their response matrices L_a, L_b respectively. Within each substance separately, the fluxes and potentials are related by

$$\vec{F} = -L_s \vec{\nabla} \phi, \quad (6)$$

with $s = a, b$. The L 's are real, symmetric, and positive-definite.

We now take the following steps, changing in each the basis of potentials and fluxes we work with. For each new basis the representation of L is changed so it still gives the fluxes in terms of the driving fields.

(i) Redefine the units of the potentials by using $\phi' = D^{-1}\phi$ so that ϕ'_k all have the same dimensions (the "physical" potentials, ϕ_i , do not, in general, all have the same dimensions); $D = \text{diag}(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n)$. Because $F_k \phi_k$ all have the same dimensions-as they all add up to give the generating function-so will all the components of $F' = DF$. (We suppress the space-vector designation unless it is explicitly needed in the expression.) In this basis the response matrices are $L' = DLD$.

(ii) Being also symmetric, L'_a can be diagonalized by an orthogonal matrix $O\tilde{O} = 1$:

$$OL'_a\tilde{O} = \ell = \text{diag}(\ell_1, \ell_2, \dots, \ell_n). \quad (7)$$

The matrix ℓ is the response matrix of substance a in the potentials $\hat{\phi} = O\phi'$ and fluxes $\hat{F} = OF'$; that of b is $OL'_b\tilde{O}$.

(iii) We now change the potentials to $\phi^* = \ell^{1/2}\hat{\phi}$ and $F^* = \ell^{-1/2}\hat{F}$. Because ℓ is positive definite $\ell^{1/2} = \text{diag}(\ell_1^{1/2}, \ell_2^{1/2}, \dots, \ell_n^{1/2})$ is real. In these potentials and fluxes substance a has a unit response matrix, and b has $L_b^* = \ell^{-1/2}ODL_bD\tilde{O}\ell^{-1/2}$ as its response matrix.

(iv) Now, L_b^* itself is symmetric and can thus be diagonalized by an orthogonal matrix P :

$$PL_b^*P = \rho = \text{diag}(\rho_1, \rho_2, \dots, \rho_n). \quad (8)$$

In our final basis-that we call an eigenbasis of the problem- $\psi = P\phi^*$; $J = PF^*$, the response matrix of b is diagonal, while that of a remains the unit matrix.

Note that $\sum \vec{J}_k \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi_k = \sum \vec{F}_k \cdot \vec{\nabla} \phi_k$; so, the generating function is invariant under the change bases we made, and the basis fluxes remain the conjugates of the basis potentials; this is true for each of the steps.

(v) Here enters physics. In the eigenbasis of the problem, every flux-potential pair is decoupled from all the others in each of the substances. In a one has $\vec{J}_k = \vec{\nabla} \psi_k$, while in b , $\vec{J}_k = \rho_k \vec{\nabla} \psi_k$.

Moreover, the eigenfluxes satisfy $\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{J}_k = 0$, because they are linear combinations-with coefficients that are fixed for the problem-of the physical fluxes \vec{F} . Hence, in any composite of a and b , an applied $\vec{\nabla}\psi_k$ for any k can drive only the flux \vec{J}_k . In other words, the response matrix of the any composite cannot connect different eigenpotentials of the problem; it is diagonal in the eigenbasis.

We proceed now to treat isotropic composites, and defer the treatment of anisotropic composites to §V.

When the composite is made so as to have isotropic response, its effective response matrix is also an $n \times n$ matrix that, as we just proved, must be diagonal in the eigenbasis. If L is the effective response matrix in the physical basis, it is

$$\lambda = P\ell^{-1/2}ODLD\hat{O}\ell^{-1/2}\tilde{P}, \quad (9)$$

in the eigenbasis. It is clear at this point that L is given, once one specifies the n values of the elements of λ ; thus, the $n(n+1)/2$ measurable elements of L -which are quite arbitrary for a general medium-must satisfy $n(n-1)/2$ constraints for the composite that depend only on the elements of L_a, L_b . We now proceed to derive these constraints.

The matrices λ and ρ representing L and L_b , respectively, in the eigenbasis, commute: $[\lambda, \rho] = 0$ which gives in turn:

$$LD\tilde{O}\ell^{-1}ODL_b - L_bD\tilde{O}\ell^{-1}ODL = 0. \quad (10)$$

But, it follows from the definitions of D, O, ℓ [eq.(7) and steps (i) (ii) above] that $D\tilde{O}\ell^{-1}OD = L_a^{-1}$, so we finally obtain the desired compatibility conditions,

$$C(L, L_a, L_b) \equiv LL_a^{-1}L_b - L_bL_a^{-1}L = 0. \quad (11)$$

This is a matrix condition that, as we have shown, must be satisfied by the response matrix, L of any isotropic composite made of two isotropic components with response matrices L_a , and L_b . It does not involve the volume fractions of the components, nor the details of the microstructure, on which each of the elements of L does depend.

We now give a compactified version of the proof which-it is hoped-makes it more transparent. Given two real, symmetric, and positive-definite matrices L_a, L_b one can-as we have shown,¹⁶ in effect-diagonalize them simultaneously by a real matrix W , such that

$$WL_a\tilde{W} = \lambda^a = \text{diag}(\lambda_1^a, \lambda_2^a, \dots, \lambda_n^a), \quad WL_b\tilde{W} = \lambda^b = \text{diag}(\lambda_1^b, \lambda_2^b, \dots, \lambda_n^b); \quad (12)$$

the matrix W is not orthogonal, in general. (In the detailed proof we had $W = P\ell^{-1/2}OD$, and $\lambda^a = 1$.) Now, if we work with the eigenpotentials and eigenfluxes:

$$\psi = \tilde{W}^{-1}\phi, \quad J = WF, \quad (13)$$

the response matrices in the two substances are given by λ^a and λ^b . We have $\sum \vec{J}_k \cdot \vec{\nabla}\psi_k = \sum \vec{F}_k \cdot \vec{\nabla}\phi_k$; so, the generating function is invariant. We now argue, as before, that the effective response matrix of the composite must also be diagonal in this basis:

$$WL\tilde{W} = \lambda = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n). \quad (14)$$

All the information on the volume fractions of the components and the microstructure of the composite enters through the constants λ_i .

Obviously, λ, λ^a , and λ^b all commute. This fact can be cast in forms that involve only L, L_a , and L_b but not W . For example, writing

$$\lambda(\lambda^a)^{-1}\lambda^b - \lambda^b(\lambda^a)^{-1}\lambda = 0, \quad (15)$$

we get immediately the compatibility conditions eq.(11). One can also write more relations such as $[\lambda^{-1}\lambda^a, \lambda^{-1}\lambda^b] = 0$ leading to $[L^{-1}L_a, L^{-1}L_b] = 0$ and others of this form; they can all be shown to be equivalent to eq.(11).

The same arguments apply for the response matrices of any three composites made of the same two components. These matrices must commute in the eigenbasis and hence in the physical basis they must satisfy the compatibility conditions. Hence, it is enough to measure the response matrices of two composites to provide constraints on any third (including any of the two components).

We now attend to cases where the response matrices are not real symmetric as we assumed in the proof. When the problem can be formulated in terms of complex potentials and fluxes with Hermitian, positive-definite response matrices, the same proof applies, mutatis mutandis, and eq.(11) must still be satisfied.

As explained in §I, many linear-response problems of interest are described complex, symmetric response matrices. Strictly speaking, our proof fails in this case because not all complex, symmetric matrices can be diagonalized by a matrix, U , satisfying $\tilde{U} = U^{-1}$ (U may now be complex). However, the set of $n \times n$ complex, symmetric matrices that cannot be diagonalized in this way is a set measure zero among all the complex, symmetric matrices. For example, for $n = 2$, only the four-real-parameter family of matrices of the form:

$$Z = \begin{pmatrix} 2z_1 & \pm i(z_1 - z_2) \\ \pm i(z_1 - z_2) & 2z_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

with z_1, z_2 arbitrary, complex numbers, cannot be diagonalized, out of the six-real-parameter set of all complex, symmetric matrices. (These are the matrices with two equal eigenvalues.) Barring such unlikely occurrences for the response matrices, the compatibility conditions must apply here as well. In the complex case the response matrices depend on the frequency, and the compatibility conditions must hold for every frequency.

IV. GENERAL PROPERTIES OF THE COMPATIBILITY RELATIONS

The compatibility conditions enjoy some very useful symmetries and superposition properties. These can be straightforwardly derived from the compatibility conditions themselves-without reference to the way in which the latter were arrived at-and we state them here without detailing the proofs.

(1) As expected, the conditions $C(L, L_a, L_b) = 0$ are symmetric in L_a and L_b . In fact, they are totally symmetric with respect to the three arguments of C . Knowledge of any two of the three constrains the third.

- (2) The conditions are satisfied automatically for the cases $L = L_a$ and $L = L_b$.
- (3) When the three arguments are diagonal, the compatibility conditions are identities, so we have nothing to add to the knowledge of such systems.
- (4) If two matrices commute, and the third is compatible with them, the latter must also commute with them.
- (5) If three matrices are compatible, so are their inverses.
- (6) If matrices L_1, L_2, \dots are compatible with L_a and L_b , so is any linear or harmonic combination of them; i.e., any matrix of the forms $\sum \nu_i L_i$, or $(\sum \nu_i L_i^{-1})^{-1}$ (ν_i are numbers). Thus, the series or parallel combination of mixtures that are compatible with two components, produces another one that is also compatible with them.

Given two of the matrix arguments of the compatibility function, the compatibility conditions constitute linear equations in the components of the third. How many independent equations do we get thus? When the response matrices are symmetric (Hermitian), as we have assumed so far, the compatibility matrix C is antisymmetric (anti-Hermitian). One then has $n(n-1)/2$ real conditions in the real case, $n(n-1)$ real conditions in the complex-symmetric case, and n^2 real conditions in the Hermitian case.

When the arguments of C have the Casimir form [eq.(5)], then C can be shown to take the form:

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} A^{(1)} & \bar{B} \\ \bar{B} & A^{(2)} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (17)$$

where $A^{(i)}$ are antisymmetric matrices. Again we see that only one set of $n(n-1)/2$ offdiagonal elements of C are independent.

Are all these conditions linearly independent? We conjecture without proof that in the generic case, where no degeneracies are present, they are. We checked this by algebraic computation technics for the case $n = 3$ (and trivially for $n = 2$) and found that, indeed, in the general case, the three compatibility equations obtained are independent: any three of the six unknowns determine the other three.

V. ANISOTROPIC COMPOSITES

Many composites, even of isotropic component, are themselves anisotropic. Such are, for instance, laminated structures, or composites in which one component is in the form of long parallel needles, or in the form of aligned, similar, triclinic grains. For arbitrary anisotropic materials exhibiting a coupled linear-response phenomenon in d space dimensions, the relations between potentials and fluxes are

$$F_{k\alpha} = \sum_{m\beta} L_{k m \alpha \beta} \partial_\beta \phi_m. \quad (18)$$

Latin indices designate the field type, as before; Greek indices designate space coordinates: $\alpha\beta = 1, \dots, d$. The response matrix is symmetric with respect to the simultaneous exchange of both: $L_{k m \alpha \beta} = L_{k m \beta \alpha}$. For a fixed pair of fields, ϕ_k, ϕ_m , let $T(km)$ be the $d \times d$ matrix whose $\alpha\beta$ element

is $L_{km\alpha\beta}$, it is the space-tensor modulus of the material (such as the heat-diffusion tensor, the dielectric tensor, the thermoelectric tensor, etc.). The T 's are, in general, asymmetric tensors, unless $k = m$, in which case the symmetry of L dictates that they are. We can write L as an $nd \times nd$ matrix of the form:

$$L = \begin{pmatrix} T(11) & T(12) & \cdots & T(1n) \\ \tilde{T}(12) & T(22) & \cdots & T(2n) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \tilde{T}(1n) & \tilde{T}(2n) & \cdots & T(nn) \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

As we argued in §III, in the eigenbasis of the problem, L must be diagonal in the field indices; i.e., the response matrix of a composite of two isotropic materials, in this basis, takes the form:

$$\lambda_{km\alpha\beta} = t_{\alpha\beta}^k \delta_{km}. \quad (20)$$

For fixed α and β we get a matrix that is diagonal in km . This implies—as all our basis changes do not act on the space indices—that for every $\alpha\beta$, L , as matrix in km must satisfy the compatibility conditions eq.(11). We thus get d^2 such matrix conditions. In other words, if in eq.(11) we put for the km -matrix element of L , the space-tensor matrix $T(km)$, we get the generalization the compatibility conditions for anisotropic composites.

Interestingly enough, we can now extract from the compatibility conditions, relations between the moduli of the composite with no information on those of the components. The mere fact that the composite is made of two isotropic components constrain its allowed response matrix.

For example, in the general case, where no special degeneracies are present, every tensor coefficient $T(km)$ can be written—through the compatibility conditions—as a linear combination of the n tensors $T(ii)$, lying along the diagonal of L . The latter are, however, all symmetric, and so must all the $T(km)$'s be. This can also be deduced from the fact that the $T(km)$ are linear combinations of the symmetric tensors t^k appearing in eq.(20). To recapitulate: all the tensor moduli of an anisotropic composite of two isotropic materials are symmetric (this is not the case for an arbitrary material).

There are additional constraints that make no use of the moduli of the components. This comes about in the following way: The response matrix of a general anisotropic material has $nd(nd+1)/2$ independent components (we confine our discussion here to the real case, the generalization to the complex case is straightforward). The compatibility conditions provide $d^2n(n-1)/2$ constraint on those, with parameters that depend on the moduli of the components. (These are, in general, independent; as we can see from eq.(20), only $nd(d+1)/2$ constants need be specified, to determine all the elements of L of the composite; thus, there must exist $d^2n(n-1)/2$ independent compatibility conditions.) The number of these parameters is smaller than the number of constraint; so, they can be eliminated, leaving some constraints that involve the moduli of the composite only. The above symmetry requirements account for some of these constraints, but some still remain.

A different—and more useful—way of perceiving the existence of such component-independent relations is as follows: The $d^2, n \times n$ matrices $\ell(\alpha\beta)$ formed from L by fixing the space indices, are diagonal in the eigenbasis, and hence, every three of them must satisfy the compatibility conditions among themselves, just as any three composite response matrices must. In such relations, the moduli of the components do not appear, and we are left with desired relations.

$$C[\ell(\alpha\beta), \ell(\gamma\delta), \ell(\epsilon\eta)] = 0, \quad (21)$$

for all the choices of the six space indices (not all of these relations are independent).

We note here that, in general, the principal axes of the different tensor coefficients, $T(km)$, need not be the same. In composites that have symmetry axes—such as laminar ones—all $T(km)$ do commute and can be diagonalized in the same axes. In this frame we have d matrices $\ell(\alpha\alpha)$; $\alpha = 1, \dots, d$. On these, we have $\binom{d}{3}$ sets of compatibility conditions each set still consisting of $n(n-1)/2$ conditions. In three dimensional composites with common principal axes, there is at least one such set of component-independent conditions—always in addition to the conditions that relate the composite to the components.

We shall demonstrate all this for the case $d = 3, n = 2$ in §VII.

VI. ELECTRICAL CIRCUITS AS DISCRETE REALIZATIONS

We now discuss electrical circuits as examples of discrete systems that are subject to the compatibility conditions. They also help shed light on the significance of the compatibility conditions for the continuous case. One need not bring the above proof to bear on circuits; the necessity of the compatibility conditions follows directly from their general properties and the construction of the circuits.

Consider electrical circuits (that we shall term n -pair circuits) having n pairs of external terminals: $1, 1'; 2, 2'; \dots, n, n'$ (n will be fixed for the rest of our discussion), with an internal structure that guarantees that the current, I_i , going into terminal i is the same as that coming out of i' . Let V_i be the voltage difference between i' and i . Suppose we describe the system by the impedance matrix Z such that the voltage vector $V = (V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n)$ is given by $V = ZI$, where $I = (I_1, I_2, \dots, I_n)$ is the vector of currents. V, I , and Z may be complex, and Z frequency dependant.

If any number of n -pair circuits with impedances Z_a, Z_b, \dots are connected in series (terminal i' of each to terminal i of the next), we get another n -pair circuit whose impedance matrix, Z , is the sum of Z_m . This is because each i -voltage on the system is the sum of the i -voltages on the component, while the currents through all the i -terminals are the same. We call this an additive connection with respect to Z . When circuits are connected in parallel (the i -terminal of all components to the same external i -terminal) the inverses of Z_m add to give the inverse of Z (the currents now add while the i voltages are the same for all the components), and we term this a harmonic connection with respect to Z .

Now, consider two n -pair circuits, a and b , with Z_a and Z_b , respectively, which we use as basic building blocks, to build any n -pair circuit following these rules: Beginning with a number of a and b circuits, we build the circuit in stages; in each stage we put together, into an n -pair circuit, either in series or in parallel, any number of n -pair circuits built by the same rules in previous stages (see Fig. 1). It is clear that the impedance matrix of the resulting circuit must satisfy the compatibility conditions with Z_a, Z_b ; so, for that matter, must the impedance matrices of any three circuits composed in this way (from the same building blocks a and b). This follows, straightforwardly, from properties (vi) of the compatibility conditions and we need not resort to the proof given for the continuous case. In fact, the compatibility conditions applies here under less stringent conditions than had been assumed in the proof.

When the circuits contain only standard elements, the Onsager theorem applies, and the impedance matrix must be symmetric. The circuit may, however, contain gyrators: time-reversal antisymmetric elements¹⁷. The matrix Z is then not symmetric but has the Casimir form. The compatibility conditions must still apply for composite n -pair circuits containing gyrators (because the additive and harmonic joining of the response matrix still applies). More generally, whenever it is possible to define an additive-and a harmonic-combination circuits with respect to some response matrix, any composite made of two building block by successive applications of these combinations must have a response matrix that satisfies the compatibility conditions with those of the two building blocks.

The n -pair circuits themselves offer more examples of such systems with asymmetric response matrices: Pick any k of the n terminal pairs-say the first k -and call them even, while the rest we call odd. Instead of working with the impedance matrix, describe the system by the matrix, N , that gives $V^* \equiv (V_1, V_2, \dots, V_k, I_{k+1}, \dots, I_n)$ in terms of $I^* \equiv (I_1, I_2, \dots, I_k, V_{k+1}, \dots, V_n)$: $V^* = NI^*$. It is straightforward to show that, if Z is symmetric,

$$Z = \begin{pmatrix} R & Q \\ \tilde{Q} & S \end{pmatrix}, \quad (22)$$

with R and S (complex) symmetric of ranks $k \times k$ and $(n - k) \times (n - k)$ respectively, (and S^{-1} exists) then, N has the form of a response matrix in the Casimir case [eq.(5)]:

$$N = \begin{pmatrix} R - QS^{-1}\tilde{Q} & QS^{-1} \\ -S^{-1}\tilde{Q} & S^{-1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

One can define connections of n -pair circuits that are additive and harmonic with respect to the N matrices. They are shown in Fig. 2 for the connections of two circuits. Here, in the additive connection, even terminals are connected in series, while odd ones are connected in parallel. In this way, the V^* -vector for the combined circuit is the sum of those of the components, while the I^* -vectors of all the components and of the composite are all equal. In the harmonic connection, the even terminals are connected in parallel and the odd ones in series. As before, all circuits hierarchically constructed from two basic units must have N -matrices that obey the compatibility conditions.

These results for circuits-for which the necessity of the compatibility conditions is quite evident-are interesting for themselves, but they may also illuminate the applicability of these conditions to continuous cases. It may well be that the appearance of a microstructure-and mixing-fraction-independent compatibility conditions is a vestige of a parallel and series combination of the two component substances to form the composite. This view may be strengthened by noting that all the moduli of an isotropic composite can be determined by cutting a thin slice of the composite, making each of its two faces an equipotential, and measuring the fluxes which will be perpendicular to the surface. In this one-dimensional configuration, it is easier to envisage the composite as being put together by a successive series and parallel joining of pieces.

What can we learn from circuits about continuous systems with Casimir-type response matrix? Does the fact that circuits of this type conform to the compatibility conditions imply that continuous systems do too? This need not be the case; the topology of wiring circuits allows one to interchange the role of any number of driving potentials and their conjugate fluxes. This can

always be used to achieve an equivalent description of the system by a symmetric response matrix. We know then that the most general composite circuit is specified by only n independent moduli. It is not surprising then that the compatibility conditions apply. In the continuous, isotropic case, all fluxes flow in the same channels, so to speak, and we cannot think of a physically meaningful description whereby some fluxes are swapped with driving forces, in a way analogous to connecting some wires in parallel instead of in series.

The validity of the compatibility conditions for the Casimir case remains an open question for us.

VII. EXAMPLES

We shall now look in some detail into the case of most immediate interest: two driving fields in three dimensions. For concreteness we shall describe the universal results in the context of the magnetoelectric effect, whereby each of the two isotropic components is described by its dielectric constant and permeability: ϵ_i , and μ_i , respectively, and by the magnetoelectric coefficient, α_i ($i = 1, 2$ for materials 1 and 2 respectively).

There is here only one compatibility relation for the effective coefficients, ϵ, μ, α , of an isotropic composite. In this, $n = 2$ case, the condition can be conveniently written as

$$\begin{vmatrix} \epsilon & \mu & \alpha \\ \epsilon_1 & \mu_1 & \alpha_1 \\ \epsilon_2 & \mu_2 & \alpha_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0, \quad (24)$$

exhibiting the symmetry of the condition in the three materials. The three triads of coefficients are in one plane in the ϵ, μ, α space.

In the degenerate case where one of the three minors multiplying one of the effective coefficients vanishes, e.g. $\epsilon_1\mu_2 - \epsilon_2\mu_1 = 0$, the condition gives a relation between the other two.

We have calculated the three effective coefficients of an isotropic composite by solving directly the field equations, with the appropriate boundary conditions, for the coated sphere composite³. In this composite, space is filled with spheres of different sizes, each made of a sphere of one material coated with a spherical shell of the other, with a fixed ratio of radii. The problem was solved exactly with the aid of computer-algebraic technics. The effective constants are rather cumbersome functions of the volume-ratio of the two components and of their constants. It was then verified that they satisfy eq.(24).

We now turn to the anisotropic case. The effective moduli ϵ, μ, α are now 3×3 tensors that, satisfy eq.(24). Because ϵ and μ must be symmetric, eq.(24) implies that α is also a symmetric space tensor-barring the degeneracy $\epsilon_1/\epsilon_2 = \mu_1/\mu_2$. Thus, an anisotropic composite of two isotropic magnetoelectric materials cannot have a vector (antisymmetric) magnetoelectric effect. This may be due to the fact that one cannot define a vector in a such a mixture.

An orthorhombic magnetoelectric material has, in general, nine independent constants, three for each modulus. An orthorhombic composite of two isotropic material has, as we now show, only eight. There are three compatibility conditions that relate those nine to the coefficients of the components. As we stated for the general case, the latter can be eliminated to give relations

between the effective constants, that require no knowledge of the components (except that they are isotropic). In our case, one such relation remains, and it can be obtained, directly, by noting that the three matrices

$$\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{zz} & \alpha_{zz} \\ \alpha_{zz} & \mu_{zz} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{yy} & \alpha_{yy} \\ \alpha_{yy} & \mu_{yy} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} & \alpha_{xx} \\ \alpha_{xx} & \mu_{xx} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (25)$$

must obey the compatibility condition eq.(24), which reads here,

$$\begin{vmatrix} \epsilon_{zz} & \mu_{zz} & \alpha_{zz} \\ \epsilon_{yy} & \mu_{yy} & \alpha_{yy} \\ \epsilon_{xx} & \mu_{xx} & \alpha_{xx} \end{vmatrix} = 0. \quad (26)$$

A general (triclinic), anisotropic material has twenty-one independent constants describing a two-field phenomenon: in our case, six each for the dielectric and permeability tensors, and nine for the magnetoelectric tensor. Our analysis shows that an anisotropic composite of two isotropic materials has only fourteen independent constants. Three of the twenty-one fall because the cross modulus must be symmetric., thus using three of the total of nine compatibility conditions—one for each pair of space indices. Of the remaining six, two can be used to eliminate the two parameters that depend on the constants of the components entering the compatibility conditions. The remaining four relations can be cast in a determinant form similar to eq.(26): In addition to eq.(26) we now write three equations with zz in the last row replaced by xy , zz , and yz . These four conditions amount to stating that the six triads $\epsilon_{\gamma\delta}, \mu_{\gamma\delta}, \alpha_{\gamma\delta}$ are in the same plane in the ϵ, μ, α plane ($\gamma, \delta = x, y, z$). (The fourteen independent constants must still obey two conditions relating them to the moduli of the components.) These are special cases of eq.(21).

When the response matrix of one component (say 2) is a multiple of the unit matrix which is the case, for example, for the effective constants of a porous magnetoelectric material (one component being vacuum)-the compatibility conditions for the tensor moduli reduce to

$$\alpha = \frac{\alpha_1}{(\epsilon_1 - \mu_1)}(\epsilon - \mu). \quad (27)$$

Thus-as the constants of the components enter through only the one parameter, $\alpha_1/(\epsilon_1 - \mu_1)$, that needs be eliminated-there are only thirteen independent constants (seven in the orthorombic case).

We calculated-by solving the Maxwell equations-the dielectric, permeability, and magnetoelectric tensor moduli for two porous media, both involving triaxial ellipsoids surrounded by vacuum. The first was the coated-ellipsoid configuration in which space is filled with similar, oriented, triaxial ellipsoids-with an assortment of sizes-each made of an inner ellipsoid of an isotropic material, surrounded by vacuum inside a larger ellipsoid confocal with the inner one; here the composite has an orthorombic symmetry (the principal axes of the three moduli are the same). The other configuration is a diluted mixture of (noninteracting) triaxial ellipsoids in vacuum, with different axes ratios and different orientations; here the three moduli may have different principal axes. As expected, we find that eq.(27) is satisfied in both cases.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

We have shown that the allowed linear-response moduli of composites made of two isotropic components are strongly constrained by a set of compatibility conditions in the form of algebraic

equations containing only the moduli of the components and of the composite. The volume fractions of the components do not appear, nor do the details of the microstructure. The same relations must be obeyed by the moduli of any three composites of the same two components, and require no knowledge of the moduli of the latter. All the response matrices of composites of the same two isotropic materials must be of the form $W^{-1}\lambda\tilde{W}^{-1}$, where λ is diagonal with elements that are positive (and conform to the known bounds on the moduli of uncoupled response matrices). For anisotropic composites of isotropic components, relations exist between the effective constants, that are altogether independent of the moduli of the components.

All through the paper we have treated the composite as homogeneous on the scale over which the gradients of the potentials are obtained from differences and over which the fluxes are averaged. In fact, however, the compatibility conditions apply under more general circumstances for a system that is not necessarily homogenized. Consider a region, R , of space, with a boundary Σ . On Σ one dictates the potentials as boundary conditions of the form:

$$\phi_m(\vec{\sigma}) = \phi_{m0}b(\vec{\sigma}); \quad \vec{\sigma} \in \Sigma, \quad (28)$$

where, $b(\vec{\sigma})$ is the same for all potentials and ϕ_{m0} are constants. (The treatment is generalized straightforwardly to the Newman boundary conditions.) The region is filled with some material and one measures the fluxes at $\vec{r} \in R$; linearity implies that the α space component of the fluxes is given by

$$F_k^\alpha(\vec{r}) = \Lambda_{km}^\alpha(\vec{r})\phi_{m0}; \quad (29)$$

$\Lambda^\alpha(\vec{r})$ may be considered the response matrix, at \vec{r} , to the potentials on Σ ; it depends on the choice of R , on $b(\vec{\sigma})$, as well as on the the distribution of L in R . When R is filled with a homogeneous, isotropic medium with a response matrix L , it is easy to see that

$$\Lambda_{km}^\alpha(\vec{r}) = -L_{km}\partial_\alpha g(\vec{r}), \quad (30)$$

where $g(\vec{r})$ is the solution of the Laplace equation in R , with $b(\vec{r})$ as boundary condition. If we now fill R with two isotropic components in whatever fashion-possibly with pieces not much smaller than R itself-we find, using arguments as in §III, that any three matrices $\Lambda^\alpha(\vec{r})$, each corresponding to an arbitrary choice of α, \vec{r}, R or $b(\vec{\sigma})$, but with the filling material being a mixture of the same two components, must satisfy the compatibility conditions among themselves. our findings for the effective response matrices of composites are all special cases of this result. Also, we see that to check our findings, experimentally, one needs not prepare a homogenized composite; for example, one can work with an arbitrary mixture filling the space between two parallel condenser plates that are each an equipotential.

Our interest here has been focused on relations that are independent of details of the preparation of the composite. We can, however, make the following note concerning bounds: There are various constraints known for uncoupled phenomena in the form bounds on the (uncoupled) moduli of the composites in terms of those of the components^{4,5}. We can now put these to use by bounding the diagonal elements of L in the eigenbasis, λ_i , in terms of λ_i^a and λ_i^b . These bounds can, in turn, be formulated as bounds on the elements of L that depend on those of L_a, L_b . We hope to demonstrate this procedure and describe the resulting bounds in a future publication

We now list some of the limitations that, think, we our analysis is subject to. We have not been able to extend the results to composites of more than two components. It is, in general, impossible

to diagonalize simultaneously three symmetric matrices in the way that underlies our derivation for two components. For a composite that is made of three components by preparing first a composite of two of them which is then mixed with the third, our analysis shows that it is enough to specify $2n$ constants for the final composite to determine all the rest (when all the samples involved are isotropic, say). But this helps only if $n > 3$, and besides, such composites are, of course, not the general three-components composites. A likewise unlikely three-phase composite is one in which the response matrix of a component is a linear combination of the other two. All matrices can then be diagonalized simultaneously, and the compatibility conditions still apply. Similar arguments apply to composites with more components.

Our method is also limited in that the changes of bases that we employ must operate on the potentials and not on the driving forces themselves as we must preserve the fact that the fields are derivable from potentials. Also diagonalizing the response matrices in the space coordinates will prove futile, as the field equations couple the coordinates. Thus, the Hall effect, and the thermomagnetic effect, are not directly amenable to our treatment. We also have not found a way to generalize our results to the general case of nonscalar potentials-such as effects involving elastic stresses-because here there is more than one way to couple the fields derived from the same potential, even in isotropic materials. Again, the need to diagonalize more than two matrices, simultaneously, would arise. In some special cases of this type where every two potentials interact through only one coupling, our results do apply for the matrices of coupling coefficients. Other exceptions are, for example, the piezoelectric and piezomagnetic effects in two dimensional composites (i.e. a cylindrical configuration) when the strains are limited to axial shears, and the components have a cubic symmetry.

We have also been limited to isotropic components. It is evident that, be this not the case, we would have effectively had to diagonalize more than two matrices simultaneously (even if a composite is prepared such that the principal axes in all the regions of a given component are all aligned). It may, however, well be that our results can be extended to include phenomena that we have excluded in this paper.

There are various approximations that are used to calculate effective moduli of composites (for example the coherent potential approximation¹⁸); For some approximations, the response matrices calculated consistently also satisfy the compatibility conditions.

We are not aware of actual data that would be pertinent to the present work.

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Figure captions

Figure 1. A composite circuit built hierarchically from two basic n -pair circuits. In each stage circuits are constructed by series and parallel connections of circuits constructed in earlier stages.

Figure 2. Connections of two n -pair circuits that are additive (a) and harmonic (b) with respect to the N response matrices described in the text.

Figure 1

Figure 2